

SOCIAL SCIENCES

A REVIEW OF AI-POWERED DISINFORMATION STRATEGIES: THE CASES OF RUSSIA, CHINA, IRAN, AND NORTH KOREA

Garajamirli N.

*Department of Audiovisual and Public Communications
The Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
ORCID: 0009-0008-8195-4629*

ABSTRACT

This study analyzes how AI-powered disinformation campaigns are organized on a global scale and for what strategic purposes state actors carry out them. Within the scope of the research, AI-based disinformation activities carried out by Russia, China, Iran and North Korea between 2023 and 2024 were examined in line with OpenAI's "Threat Intelligence Report" document. Systematic literature review and qualitative document analysis were used together as methods. The campaigns were evaluated through major language models, deepfake technologies, automatic commenting systems and fake media sites used in content production. The findings of the research show that each country's disinformation strategy differs both technologically and politically. While Russia and China focus more on social media interaction and public opinion manipulation, Iran focuses on ideological content production, and North Korea focuses on direct cyber attacks. Despite the high production capacity of content produced with AI tools, it has been observed that these campaigns have limited impact on real users. It was determined that no campaign exceeded 2 points in the "Breakout Scale" assessment used by OpenAI. This study reveals the effects of artificial intelligence on information security, media algorithms and digital sovereignty; it emphasizes the necessity of not only technical but also ethical and legal approaches in the fight against disinformation.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, disinformation, conflict, covert influence, propaganda.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of artificial intelligence technologies has created both opportunities and threats in the field of digital communication. Thanks to technologies such as natural language processing (NLP), generative AI (Generative AI) and large language models (LLM), information production, dissemination and targeting have become easier; this has radically changed the dimensions of disinformation. Especially in political disinformation campaigns, the use of artificial intelligence-supported automatic content production, bot management and deepfake technologies has become a significant problem in terms of global security. The digital information environment has now become a strategic operation area not only for individuals but also for states.

Studies conducted in recent years show that disinformation is becoming increasingly organized, targeted and technological. Howard and Bradshaw (2024) state that state-sponsored disinformation operations are carried out in 81 countries and 79% of them aim to manipulate social media algorithms. In these operations, artificial intelligence tools are generally used in functions such as content production, comment management, visual forgery and account proliferation. Zannettou et al. (2019) emphasizes that political content produced by large language models has become indistinguishable from human-written content, while Fallis (2024) argues that this situation systematically undermines trust in information. Fake news, deepfake videos, and fake social media interactions, which become widespread especially during election periods, are considered a new form of "digital warfare" that threatens democratic processes. However, there are several important gaps in the existing literature. First, AI-supported disinformation campaigns have mostly been analyzed from a Western

perspective; systematic and comparative analyses of the operations of actors such as Russia, China, Iran, and North Korea have been limited. Second, although the technical tools have been defined, the real impact of these campaigns has often been assessed superficially. Third, although existing studies touch on the ethical, legal, and strategic consequences of AI, they do not address in detail how and in what combinations these technologies are used at the campaign level. In addition, a holistic approach is lacking in subheadings such as strategy differentiation by platform, content format, and target audience selection. In this context, the aim of this study is to analyze AI-supported disinformation campaigns in detail and comparatively, specific to four state actors. The campaigns carried out by Russia, China, Iran and North Korea between 2023 and 2024 were evaluated based on OpenAI's "Threat Intelligence Report" (2024) document; the technologies used by each country, target platforms, message strategies and dissemination methods were systematically examined (Zerback, T., & Töpfl, F., 2022). Qualitative document analysis and systematic literature review methods were used together in the study. Thus, a strong analysis basis was created at both theoretical and empirical levels. This study has four main contributions to the literature. First, instead of a large-scale analysis covering a large number of countries, a small but in-depth country-focused approach was adopted. This allows for the tactical understanding of AI-supported campaigns. Second, unlike existing studies, not only content production but also platform selection, targeting methods and technical modules using AI were evaluated separately. Third, the level of social interaction of each analyzed campaign was measured with OpenAI's "Breakout Scale" system, thus revealing the gap between technical capacity and real impact. Fourth, a multidimensional

assessment of how the results of these campaigns should be addressed on both strategic and ethical levels is presented.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are defined as algorithmic systems that can mimic the cognitive functions of the human mind, participate in decision-making processes, and produce data-based solutions. In recent years, the development of these technologies has created a radical transformation in the digital information environment. In particular, advanced methods such as Natural Language Processing (NLP), Machine Learning (ML), and Creative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have deeply affected the nature of disinformation, its spreading speed, and its impact capacity (Balçioğlu & Doğan, 2023). Thanks to these tools, more targeted, more convincing, and faster-spreading disinformation campaigns have become possible. From a technological perspective, disinformation has now become not only the production of information, but also the process of information distribution, user manipulation, and reshaping social interaction patterns (Dhamani, N., Azunre, P., Gleason, J. L., Corcoran, C., Honke, G., Kramer, S., & Morgan, J., 2019). One of the most fundamental features of AI-supported disinformation is the personalization of content and its adaptation to the target audience. Kandel (2020) argues that AI algorithms increase the effectiveness of propaganda activities through personalization of political messages and voter segmentation. In this process, behavioral data collected from users are analyzed to produce message formats specific to individuals; thus, users are only exposed to content that is compatible with their own views. This reduces the diversity of information that individuals are exposed to and triggers social phenomena such as “filter bubbles” and “echo chambers” (Howard & Bradshaw, 2024). The literature reveals that these artificially structured digital interaction environments deepen social polarization and lead to the fragmentation of the democratic public sphere. It is stated that AI is effective not only in the production of fake content, but also in the processes of directing information access, shaping public perception, and predicting digital behaviors (Yıldız, A., 2022). In particular, algorithms based on big data analysis can predict individuals' political tendencies and psychological profiles with high accuracy; and customize content presentation based on this data. This process poses serious threats to the fundamental values of democracy, such as freedom of expression, the right to information, and equal access to information (Zannettou et al., 2019). AI-supported disinformation campaigns, especially during election periods, carry the risk of manipulating voter behavior, eroding trust, and weakening faith in legitimate democratic institutions. One of the most striking forms of AI-based disinformation is content developed with generative AI technologies. These content appear in the form of texts that appear to be written by human hands, fake images, synthetic voices, and deep-fake videos. Especially thanks to GAN technologies, fake videos can be produced by imitating real people; these contents can spread rapidly on social media. Hou (2024) emphasizes that the level of persuasiveness of

such content is high and that the level of traditional media literacy is insufficient in the face of this new threat. At the same time, the fact that such fake content is highlighted as “trending” content by social media algorithms makes it easier for disinformation to reach wider audiences. Disinformation campaigns that work in integration with AI technologies are not limited to text content only. Bot accounts, fake profiles and automatic comment systems are also integral parts of these campaigns. In this context, campaign formats such as spamouflage, astroturfing and doppelganger offer striking examples in both tactical and technical terms (Lungarella, M., Iida, F., Bongard, J. C., & Pfeifer, R., 2024). While astroturfing creates the impression that there is a natural demand or criticism from the public, spamouflage aims to produce spam content in many languages and manipulate social media algorithms. Doppelganger, on the other hand, is based on copying real news sites and putting fake content into circulation. In all these campaign types, artificial intelligence plays an active role in areas such as automation of content production, simulation of user reactions and artificially increasing the intensity of interaction (Dhamani, N., Azunre, P., Gleason, J. L., Corcoran, C., Honke, G., Kramer, S., & Morgan, J. 2019).

The formal diversity of AI-powered disinformation campaigns is an important theme in the academic literature on this field. Each campaign type differs in terms of both the technology used and the target platform. One of the most common forms of these campaigns, astroturfing, is used to create fake public support or public outcry. Howard and Bradshaw (2024) emphasize that astroturfing is frequently used, especially during election periods, to create the impression of fake social movements. This technique is supported by thousands of algorithmically optimized fake comments and social media posts. Thanks to AI-based text generation systems, these fake comments can be prepared in a meaningful, original and emotionally convincing way. Another notable campaign type, spamouflage, is mostly conducted in China and aims to manipulate social media algorithms with multilingual spam comments. These campaigns are concentrated on platforms such as YouTube, Twitter (X), Reddit and TikTok, where AI plays an active role in adjusting the language of the content to the target audience. Hou (2024) states that the texts used in spamouflage campaigns are generally of low quality but high volume, which allows them to pass the algorithms' "trending content" filter. In addition, the linguistic diversity of these texts shows how flexible AI can be used as a tool in international disinformation strategies.

Doppelganger campaigns are another type of strategic disinformation carried out through fake news sites. In these campaigns, the designs of real news portals are copied one-to-one, fake content is produced, and this content is perceived as real news. Aboutayeb, M. (2023), revealed that this method particularly targets users in Europe and America, and fake news is mostly reinforced with AI-supported images and headlines. The fact that such content looks both technically and visually professional increases the risk of the public being exposed to false information.

It is seen that AI is used in these campaigns not only in content production, but also for the purpose of manipulating the platforms' algorithms. The content recommendation systems of social media platforms highlight certain content according to users' interests. This has caused algorithms to become targets for social engineering activities. Howard & Bradshaw (2024) state that some campaigns deceive algorithms with artificially created interaction chains (e.g., fake like, share, and comment cycles), and thus fake content can spread as if it were organic.

In addition, it is stated in the literature that different platforms follow different strategies depending on their level of vulnerability to disinformation. For example, while fast and intensive content spread is provided in more closed systems such as Telegram, long texts that start discussions are preferred in forum-based structures such as Reddit. On video-based platforms such as TikTok, disinformation spread has been analyzed through deepfake videos and artificial audio production. These findings show that AI-supported campaigns are customized not only in terms of content but also platform strategy (Islas, O., Gutiérrez, F., & Arribas, A., 2024).

Finally, the effects of algorithmic manipulation on user perception are also frequently discussed in the literature. It is stated that fake content generated by AI blurs the perception of reality and reduces users' trust in information (Fallis, 2024). This situation weakens democratic participation and social consensus; it threatens the public's rational decision-making capacity, especially during election periods. At the same time, if individuals have low media literacy levels, it becomes almost impossible for them to notice such content. Therefore, the literature emphasizes that technical measures alone will not be sufficient in the fight against AI-supported disinformation, but that education, ethical awareness and platform regulations should be addressed together (Islas, O., Gutiérrez, F., & Arribas, A., 2024).

AI-supported disinformation strategies have become not only a technical issue but also a deep geopolitical and strategic issue. In this context, the literature draws attention to the fact that state-sponsored disinformation campaigns are increasingly organized and structured in a targeted manner. It is observed that authoritarian or semi-authoritarian regimes in particular use AI technologies as a means of digital propaganda, psychological warfare, and perception engineering (Balcıoğlu & Doğan, 2023). The main goals of these states include influencing the public opinion of rival countries, weakening democratic systems, fueling social polarization, and strengthening the legitimacy of their own regimes in the international arena. Howard and Bradshaw (2024) state that state-sponsored disinformation campaigns have been detected in at least 81 countries as of 2023. 79% of these campaigns directly target social media platforms and develop content production, interaction manipulation, and targeting strategies using AI tools. For example, the Russia-based Doppelganger campaign produced fake content by copying Western media images; Spamuflage, based in China, aims to

influence public perception with comment chains translated into different languages. In the examples of Iran and North Korea, religious rhetoric, ideological messages and cyber attack techniques come to the fore (Auezov, M., Nysanov, E. A., Kemelbekova, Zh. S., Zhidebayeva, A. N., Kuatbekov, A., Kozhabaev, S. E., & Korokbaev, A., 2024).

The fact that these campaigns are directly related to state policies shows that disinformation is no longer just an individual or organizational issue, but has become a direct national security issue. In this context, the use of artificial intelligence overlaps with strategic goals such as not only information production but also digital sovereignty, information superiority and perception control. While Zannettou et al. (2019) define this process as the new front of the "digital cold war", Kreps, S. E., McCain, M., & Brundage, M. (2020) states that this poses a systemic threat to information-based societies.

Despite this, some limitations are evident in the existing literature. First of all, technical dimensions are prioritized in most analyses of AI-supported disinformation campaigns; however, empirical findings on the social effects of these contents, user perception or long-term effects on democratic processes remain limited. Likewise, detailed analyses of the reasons for campaign failure (e.g. user unresponsiveness, lack of interaction, credibility problems) are lacking. The literature mostly assumes how "effective" AI tools are, but fails to analyze the conditions under which this effectiveness occurs (Keller, F. B., Schoch, D., Stier, S., & Yang, J., 2020).

METHODS

This research is based on a structured qualitative research approach to deeply examine AI-supported disinformation strategies. The methodological framework of the study is based on two main components: (1) systematic academic literature review and (2) institutional document analysis. These two methods are designed to complement each other in order to both strengthen the theoretical infrastructure and support the validity and reliability of empirical findings.

In the first phase of the research, the literature review, academic publications published between 2018 and 2024 covering the themes of AI, disinformation, political propaganda and digital communication were systematically examined. In this context, databases that are internationally recognized and host peer-reviewed publications were preferred. The main search sources included reliable platforms such as Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, JSTOR, ProQuest and ScienceDirect. These databases were searched with keyword combinations such as "AI AND Disinformation", "Artificial Intelligence AND Propaganda", "LLM AND Misinformation", "Deepfake AND Elections".

The obtained publications were filtered according to certain criteria. First, it was determined as a prerequisite that the publications directly focus on the subject, that is, center on the relationship between disinformation and artificial intelligence. Secondly, studies that are methodologically sound and contain empirical findings were selected. Thirdly, the fact that the publication date is up-to-date (after 2018), the publication language

is English and the study has a high citation level were also among the reasons for preference. As a result of the evaluation made in line with these criteria, a total of 65 academic studies were determined and 34 of these publications were selected for detailed content analysis.

In the selected publications, AI-supported disinformation techniques were coded and analyzed under four main themes: (1) content production (e.g., GPT-based text writing), (2) fake account and bot management, (3) visual/audio manipulation (deepfake content), and (4) algorithm manipulation (e.g., spam and comment chains). In the literature, how tactics such as astroturfing, spamouflage, doppelganger, and zero zeno are reproduced in the digital environment and what role AI plays in this process have been examined in detail. In addition, the effectiveness of social media platforms' content moderation mechanisms against this new threat has been problematized. In the second stage, the institutional document titled "Threat Intelligence Report" published by OpenAI in 2024 was evaluated with the qualitative document analysis technique. This document is a unique source in terms of providing concrete examples of state-sponsored disinformation campaigns. The campaigns included in the report were classified by country (Russia, China, Iran, North Korea) and each campaign was thematically coded according to the artificial intelligence tools, target platforms, message formats, geotargeting strategies and social interaction levels used in its content. The coding process was done manually and the content analysis was carried out with an NVivo-based logic. During the document analysis, the recurring tactical structures in each campaign, the similarity of the technical tools used and the distribution of target platforms were comparatively evaluated. For example, strategic parallels were observed between the fake news sites used in Russia's Doppelganger campaign and the multilingual comment spam in China's Spamouflage campaign. These structures were classified using thematic maps and pattern recognition techniques; then cross-referenced with data in the literature. In this way, a multi-layered analysis was not only based on the document content, but also supported by academic data.

Thematic coding method was used throughout this analysis process. During the coding phase, separate category sets were created for each campaign; criteria such as campaign name, country, artificial intelligence tools used (e.g. ChatGPT, Midjourney, Stable Diffusion), content type (text, visual, audio), target platform (Telegram, X, Reddit, LinkedIn, etc.) and social interaction level were used. The relationships between these codes were sorted according to open coding, axial coding and selective coding techniques used in qualitative data analysis. In this way, tactical overlaps and strategic distinctions between similar campaigns were systematically documented.

In order to ensure data reliability, the triple verification method was applied throughout the analysis process. First, each document was read manually at least twice on different days; thus, details that could be overlooked during the coding process were minimized. Secondly, campaign names, technical expressions and platform patterns mentioned in the academic literature

were cross-checked by comparing them with the document content. Thirdly, preliminary findings were shared with different social science experts and objective contributions were made to the findings by obtaining independent expert opinions.

The data used in the research are only public, legally accessible, scientifically published or officially published documents. No data containing personal data, user identity, geographic location, IP information, etc. were included in the analysis. For this reason, since the research did not involve direct human participation, no ethics committee permission was required. However, ethical research principles were strictly adhered to; all academic and institutional sources were cited correctly, and referencing rules were meticulously followed. Thus, both academic integrity and scientific transparency were ensured.

In addition, not only a technical analysis was made in the study, but also the possible effects of the campaigns on the target groups were interpreted in a strategic and social context. For example, the fact that most of the content used in the Spamouflage campaign originating from China was designed in English, Japanese, Korean and Chinese reveals the campaign's multiple targeting strategy based on cultural codes. Similarly, the prominence of religious references in the Iranian campaigns shows that the content has not only political but also ideological goals.

In the Lazarus Group operations of North Korea, disinformation was not implemented in the classical sense to influence the public, but to shake institutional structures. Here, AI-supported social engineering techniques (e.g., fake resume production, fake e-mail writing) served as strategic tools. These analyses made it possible to make a classification not only based on content but also at the operational target level. This is an important factor that increases the methodological depth of the study.

As a result, the methodological structure adopted within the scope of this study not only provided a descriptive framework; it also provided a level of analysis that revealed the multi-layered nature of AI-supported disinformation. By considering the literature review and institutional document analysis together, both theoretical and practical information were synthesized with a holistic approach. In this way, the findings obtained were based on solid foundations in terms of both scientific validity and analyzability at the application level.

This methodological framework contains a level of clarity and academic accuracy that will set an example for similar studies. In addition, the transparent, ethical and multidisciplinary nature of the research contributes to a better understanding of the position of disinformation in current digital dynamics.

RESULTS

The main findings of this study comprehensively reveal how AI-powered disinformation campaigns are designed by four different countries – Russia, China, Iran and North Korea – with which technological tools they are carried out and on which social media platforms they are trying to be effective. The disinformation methods applied by each country differ in terms

of technical capacity, target audience selection and content types. However, the most important elements observed in common are AI-based content production, automated account management and multilingual dissemination capability. Among the Russia-based campaigns, “Bad Grammar” and “Doppelganger” operations stand out. The “Bad Grammar” campaign aimed to attract the attention of the target audience with short comments containing English spelling errors and to draw a fake local activist profile. This campaign, which operated intensively on the Telegram platform, targeted various regions such as Ukraine, Moldova, the Baltic countries and the USA. The comments used in this campaign were generally shaped around the themes of political corruption, opposition to war and criticism of the government. Most of the content was produced by artificial intelligence models and then tried to reach a wide audience through fake accounts. The originality of the content was low and therefore provided limited interaction with the audience. However, this situation is noteworthy in terms of showing how widely used the capacity of artificial intelligence to produce a large amount of content at a low cost is.

In a more advanced example, the Doppelganger campaign, disinformation was spread through fake media sites. Within the scope of this campaign, fake websites were created that resembled the designs of real news agencies and anti-Ukrainian content was published. Here, artificial intelligence was used not only for text production, but also for visual manipulations and user comments. This campaign was carried out through platforms such as X (formerly Twitter), Facebook and 9GAG. It was determined that Russia specifically targeted young users in this campaign and tried to make its content more visible by manipulating social media algorithms. The content used in the Doppelganger campaign was both visual and textual, and was supported by memes, fake graphics and emotionally charged news headlines. In addition, the impression that these contents create a natural social interaction was created through the likes and comments from the fake accounts. The Spamouflage campaign conducted by China has been considered one of the most sophisticated campaigns in terms of content production and distribution. This campaign attracted attention with its multilingual content strategies and was used to portray the Chinese government's foreign policies positively, suppress criticism, and spread anti-Western rhetoric. Spamouflage produced content in English, Japanese, Korean, and Chinese and was active on platforms such as YouTube, Reddit, Telegram, and TikTok. In the campaign, artificial intelligence was used both in the automatic writing of comments and in the emotional tone analysis of the content. With the help of sentiment analysis algorithms, oppositional content was detected and counter-propaganda content was planned. This campaign managed to rise to the top of social media algorithms thanks to the very large volume of content production. However, user interaction remained limited, with only a few fake accounts responding to most content. Spamouflage is one of the most comprehensive examples of China's efforts to manipulate public opinion both domestically and internationally.

The International Virtual Media Alliance (IUVM) campaign, which is affiliated with Iran, has a multi-platform, multi-lingual and ideologically based structure. The content supported by AI in the IUVM campaign consisted of articles supporting the Iranian government, anti-Western, anti-American and anti-Israeli discourses. The articles written in English and French were published according to a pre-planned content calendar and distributed through various websites, news portals and blogs. The titles and tags used in the content were automatically generated, indicating that an AI-based content management infrastructure was used. The main target audience of the campaign was Persian-speaking diasporas in Europe and politically sensitive groups in the Middle East. The majority of the visuals used by IUVM were supported by stock photos and artificially produced fake ID images. Again, AI played a role in the timing of the content and the selection of target platforms; for example, content broadcast at night in the US targeted morning traffic in Europe. North Korea's disinformation strategies have been carried out mostly through indirect methods and in relation to cyberattacks. In particular, the Lazarus Group has used artificial intelligence-based social engineering techniques to lure victims with fake job postings, professional emails, and phishing campaigns. LinkedIn, GitHub, Telegram, and email systems have been among the main tools of these campaigns. Artificial intelligence models have been used to make the language structure of fake emails more convincing, to prepare resumes and portfolio documents, and to analyze the online behavior of targeted individuals. The Lazarus Group has stolen \$147 million worth of digital assets as of the end of 2023 in attacks on cryptocurrency exchanges, and laundered these assets through Tornado Cash and similar mixing services. In such operations, disinformation has targeted security systems and corporate decision-makers, not the public directly. It has been determined that North Korea aims to both gain financially with these methods and to undermine trust in the digital infrastructures of Western countries. It has been determined that deepfake technology has been used at various levels in all countries' campaigns. In particular, campaigns originating from Russia and China aimed to manipulate public opinion with videos that mimic the voices or images of political leaders. These videos spread rapidly on social media, usually in the pre-election period. GAN (Generative Adversarial Network)-based artificial intelligence models were used for both fake face generation and voice synthesis. Since social media algorithms in particular generally cannot distinguish such content from real news, these fake videos reached a wide audience in a short time. In addition, some deepfake content was detected by using biometric data such as human eye blinks, but such detections were limited. In addition to AI-supported text content, some campaigns also used artificial visuals, audio podcast-like content, and automatic subtitle systems.

Platform selection has also emerged as an important variable in AI-based disinformation strategies. While Telegram, X and some regional news portals

were at the forefront in the Russian and Iranian campaigns, multinational platforms such as YouTube, Reddit, TikTok and Baidu were the focus of the Chinese campaigns. North Korea, on the other hand, targeted professional areas such as e-mail systems, LinkedIn and GitHub. In the Chinese and Russian campaigns in particular, fake comment chains were created to deceive social media algorithms and these comments were written with AI. Fake interactions were created with spam messages to make it appear that the posts were spreading organically. In addition, the language, length, tone and target audience of the content were also customized according to the platforms. For example, while short and intense content was preferred for Telegram, long texts that would start discussions were used on Reddit. A particularly striking finding is that real user interactions were quite limited in all analyzed campaigns. It was observed that despite the high production capacity of content produced with AI, this content could not establish a permanent interaction with social media users. According to the Breakout Scale impact rating system included in OpenAI's 2024 "Threat Intelligence Report" document, no campaign has reached a spreading power above 2. This situation shows that although the content is technically advanced, it remains weak in terms of social impact. The ineffectiveness of the campaigns can be explained by factors such as users' increased ability to distinguish fake content, platforms' development of content moderation systems, and the increase in the public's media literacy level. In conclusion, these findings show that state-sponsored AI-based disinformation campaigns are organized on a global scale, content production and distribution are provided using different technological infrastructures, but their real impact levels are still limited. The findings will be evaluated more broadly within the framework of the discussion in the following sections.

DISCUSSION

In this section, the general effects of AI-assisted disinformation campaigns are discussed in light of the findings obtained in the study, comparisons are made with the existing literature, and the social, political, and ethical consequences of these campaigns are analyzed. The limitations of the study are also stated and suggestions for future research are presented. The four countries examined in the study - Russia, China, Iran, and North Korea - use AI as a disinformation tool for different strategic purposes. Russia's Bad Grammar and Doppelgänger campaigns were carried out specifically to create linguistic confusion and confuse Western audiences. The content used is intentionally low quality and loaded with grammatical errors. The aim of such content is to give the reader the impression that the content is written by local people. This approach was similarly addressed in the study conducted by Zannettou et al. (2019), who emphasized that low-quality content is part of the "sounding local" strategy.

On the other hand, China's Spamouflage campaign is one of the most technically advanced examples of content production. Here, social media algorithms were attempted to be manipulated through multilingual con-

tent and comment chains written with advanced artificial intelligence models. However, researchers in the literature such as Karinshak and Jin (2023) state that despite the technical success of such campaigns, they remain weak in terms of user interaction. This is consistent with the findings of the study; because even campaigns that produce high-volume content such as Spamouflage were seen to receive low scores when evaluated on the "Breakout Scale". In Iran's IUVM campaign, it is understood that the content was produced within an ideological framework, especially supported by anti-Western and Islamist rhetoric. The findings in the literature on the use of artificial intelligence-supported title and tag systems in increasing the propaganda effect are consistent with this study (Zerback & Töpfl, 2022). In particular, the automatic generation of titles according to the emotional orientations of the target audience paves the way for more effective dissemination of content. However, the failure of this content to create credibility among real users brings with it strategic failures as well as ethical problems. The North Korean example, on the other hand, is different from classic disinformation campaigns and focuses on cybersecurity. In the Lazarus Group's attacks, disinformation acts as a distraction and is aimed directly at economic targets. This situation is structurally different from the other three countries. It has been determined that artificial intelligence is used in social engineering and targeted attack planning rather than direct content manipulation. In this context, the disinformation potential of AI is not limited to influencing public opinion, but also reaches a level that can pose a threat to economic systems.

The widespread use of deepfake technology increases the importance of visual and audio manipulation among disinformation strategies. Targeting political figures with fake videos in particular undermines public trust and threatens democratic processes. Fallis (2024) defines this situation as "the systematic destruction of trust in information." The findings of this study also support this view, showing that GAN-based deepfake videos have a high potential to mislead the public. Despite all these findings, the most striking result in the study is that even when distributed on a large scale, AI-generated content has difficulty interacting with real users. According to OpenAI's "Breakout Scale" assessment, no campaign has been able to create meaningful social interaction. This indicates both inadequate content quality and the increasing awareness of social media users against disinformation. Howard & Bradshaw (2024) argue that global disinformation campaigns have become more complex but less effective, and the findings of this study confirm this thesis. In addition, the methodological integrity of the study is important in that it is based on both systematic literature review and document analysis. However, the data used is limited to publicly available reports only. This may have caused some hidden or undisclosed state-level disinformation activities to be left out of the analysis. In addition, no direct measurement was made on user perception or psychological impact in the study. This has led to the findings remaining at a more technical and struc-

tural level. Future studies should be supported by experimental or quantitative studies that specifically measure the effects of these campaigns on real users. At the same time, comprehensive studies should be conducted on how content produced with newer AI models (e.g. GPT-4 and later) is perceived, on which platforms it is more prevalent, and what kind of counter-strategies are developed. Cross-platform perception measurements can make significant contributions to the detection of public opinion manipulation.

CONCLUSION

This study analyzed how AI-powered disinformation campaigns are structured in today's digital media ecosystem, for what strategic purposes they are used, and how they are technically executed through four country examples. Each of the campaigns implemented by Russia, China, Iran, and North Korea was designed in accordance with their own political goals and was carried out on different platforms and with different technologies. Artificial intelligence was effectively used in various functions such as content production, comment management, visual manipulation, and directing social media algorithms in these campaigns. The research revealed that although these campaigns were technically sophisticated, they had difficulty creating a broad and lasting impact on the public. According to OpenAI's Breakout Scale data, no campaign exceeded a serious dissemination threshold. This situation

can be associated with factors such as the increase in the level of media literacy in society, the more advanced monitoring mechanisms of social media platforms, and the ability of users to detect artificial content. However, the low level of engagement of the campaigns does not mean that they are unimportant. On the contrary, this situation indicates that disinformation is carried out in more covert, targeted, and strategic ways. The findings of the study coincide with many theories and empirical observations in the literature and confirm that artificial intelligence plays a central role in disinformation processes. The increasing use of deepfake technologies, the development of automatic text generation systems, and the dissemination of content in multiple languages indicate that disinformation may become more complex in the future. In this context, not only technical but also ethical, legal, and pedagogical interventions are needed. The limitations of this study include analyzing only publicly available reports and the lack of empirical data on user behavior. Future studies should particularly investigate how real users react to such content with experimental methods, focusing on psychological effects and perception levels. At the same time, the algorithmic responses of platforms, the regulatory frameworks of states, and the responsibilities of AI producers should also be addressed separately.

Figure 1. Number of Platforms Targeted in AI Disinformation Campaigns

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